

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**NEONATAL ASPHYXIA: AN ICU BASED STUDY ABOUT
GENDER INVOLVEMENT FROM LAHORE GENERAL
HOSPITAL, PAKISTAN****Saeed Ahmed Shaikh¹, Abdul Hameed Radhan², Muhammad Asim³, Agha Shabbir Ali⁴,
Abdul Rehman Siyal⁵, Mushtaque Ali Shah⁶**¹MBBS, MD(Pediatrics), Consultant Pediatrician, Department of Pediatrics, Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences Jamshoro, Sindh, Pakistan²MBBS, FCPS (Pediatrics), Assistant Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Liaquat University Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshoro, Sindh, Pakistan³MBBS, FCPS Trainee (Pediatrics), CPSP Karachi, Sindh, Pakistan⁴MBBS, FCPS (Pediatrics), Professor and HOD, Department of Pediatrics, Lahore General Hospital, Ameer Uddin Medical College, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan⁵MBBS, DCH, MD (Pediatrics), Associate Professor, Department of Pediatrics Liaquat University Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshoro, Sindh, Pakistan⁶MBBS, FCPS (Pediatrics), Senior Registrar, Department of Paediatrics, Liaquat University Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshoro, Sindh, Pakistan**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

A common neonatal nursery problem is asphyxia that is significantly responsible for neonatal morbidity as well as neonatal mortality. This cross sectional research study was conducted on full term newborns with asphyxia at Neonatal Intensive Care Unit of Pediatrics Unit-1 at Lahore General Hospital. There were 270 full term newborns with history of birth asphyxia 173(64%) out of which were male whereas 97(36%) were female. Analysis of data was managed on SPSS version 22nd frequency and percentage was calculated.

Conclusion: *Asphyxia was more common in male neonates as compared to females*

Key Words: *Full Term Neonates, Pre Term Neonates, Morbidity, Asphyxia*

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Please cite this article in press Saeed Ahmed Shaikh et al., *Neonatal Asphyxia: An ICU Based Study About Gender Involvement From Lahore General Hospital, Pakistan.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(01).

INTRODUCTION:

Pediatricians have been dealing with perinatal asphyxia since many centuries and its relationship with various organs was extensively studied [1]. Birth asphyxia results into deaths of 23% to more than 40% neonates in developing countries however it is much lower (<0.1%) in developed countries as their primary health care and obstetric health care systems[2,3]. According to WHO the estimated birth asphyxia cases are 4 - 9 million/year resulting into death of as many as 1.2 million/year neonates and rest of them suffer from cerebral palsy, epilepsy and developmental delay etc [4,5]. Asphyxia in most case results in either antepartum or intrapartum time period due to abnormalities in gas exchange (decreased Oxygen entry and Carbon dioxide removal) across the placenta while asphyxia may occur in postpartum duration but associated with secondary abnormalities of cardiovascular, neurological and pulmonary origin[5-7]. There are certain factors like hypertension, Infection, hyperglycemia, hypotension, vascular diseases, drug use placental infarction, abruptio placentae, uterine rupture, abnormalities of cord (prolapse, true knot) cyanotic heart disease, cardiomyopathy, fetal sepsis and vascular malformations that may increase the chances of developing perinatal asphyxia[8-11]. If the duration of asphyxia is brief there will be an initial rise and subsequent fall of heart rate resulting into milder rise of blood pressure and CVP without affecting the cardiac output

significantly that redistributes the cardiac output towards central nervous system, adrenal glands termed as diving reflex, if the duration of asphyxia is short but severe this redistribution of blood to deeper brain centers is compromised causing damage to the sub cortical and brain stem nuclei [12]. If the duration of asphyxia is longer cerebral blood flow will be decreased due to hypotension leading to anaerobic metabolism and causing diffuse insult to cortical and sub-cortical structures.

METHADODOLOGY:

All full term newborns with history of birth asphyxia were included excluding the neonates born with conditions other than asphyxia. Information was collected on designed study proforma for this study of questionnaire nature. Asphyxia was diagnosed according to international protocols. Consent was taken from parents and ethical approval was taken from institutional ERC prior to study commencement. Data analysis was accomplished using SPSS version 22.

RESULTS:

There were total 270 newborns with history of birth asphyxia out of which 173(64%) neonates were male and 97(36%) were female[Table-1, Figure-1]. APGAR score was 3 in 10(3.7%) neonates whereas it was 4 in 58(21.5%) neonates and the APGAR score of 5 was observed in 112(41.5%) neonates while 90(33.3%) neonates were found with APGAR score of 6[Table-II, Figure-II].

Table-I: Gender distribution of study neonates

S. No	Gender of neonates	Frequency and percentage
1.	Male	173 (64%)
2.	Female	97 (36%)
3.	Total	270 (100%)

Figure-1: Pie chart representation of study population

Table-II: APGAR Score at birth (Recorded after 5 minutes of birth)

S. No	APGAR Score	Frequency and percentage
4.	3	10 (3.7%)
5.	4	58 (21.5%)
6.	5	112 (41.5%)
7.	6	90 (33.3%)
8.	Total	270(100%)

Figure-II: Bar chart of APGAR Score

DISCUSSION:

Aliyu I et al (2017) reported 257 cases diagnosed as perinatal asphyxia out of which 149 (60.3%) were males and 98 (39.7%) were females that is consistent with the results of our current study [13]. Asad NK et al (2014) in their study on 196 asphyxia cases reported 125 (64%) males and 71 (36%) females which is also consistent with our study findings [14]. Sweta KG et al (2014) among their 125 cases of birth asphyxia also reported 90 (72.0%) as male infants and 35 (28.0%) as female infants that fall consistent to our results which show more male infants than females [15]. Study by Boskabadi H et al (2015) reported mean APGAR score of 5.98 ± 1.68 in their Asphyxia population of neonates that is also consistent to our results [5]. There exist developmental differences between male and female newborns and fetoneonatal transition as well as postnatal morbidity. Male are born premature more commonly as compared to female infants who are born with organ maturity that is the possible reason behind respiratory distress, infant mortality and worse long-term outcomes in males [16]. There were certain limitations in our study like we could not evaluate the maternal and neonatal factors responsible for birth asphyxia and long term outcomes as a result of asphyxia in our study population so we recommend this for others.

CONCLUSION:

Birth asphyxia is more common in males than females

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